

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen and Nicole Lieb

Research Center for Public Procurement Law and Administrative Cooperations
Ludwig Maximilians University of Munich

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
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Germany

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen, Nicole Lieb
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Leonhard Niederwimmer/Pixabay

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.4. Digitalization of the Administration in Bavaria

Philip Nedelcu, *Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

Relevance of the Practice

Digitalization is the aim of many current projects, both in the private and the public sector. This has been further intensified by the enactment of a federal law (OZG)¹⁴⁶ that obliges all governmental agencies to offer their services online until end of 2022.¹⁴⁷ While the law on *Länder* level (the Law on E-Government in Bavaria)¹⁴⁸ does not contain a similar obligation,¹⁴⁹ the local governments (LGs) are also bound by the OZG. To support this mandatory digitalization on the municipal level, the *Land* government engages in several projects and initiatives to nudge and support LGs in their digitalization efforts. Hence, the field of digitalization is a very current example for intergovernmental cooperation, while many projects are of course still in their early stages. As the digitalization of public administration requires a sufficient network infrastructure, the obligation to digitalize described below may have beneficial side effects for rural areas that so far lack sufficient infrastructure and a stable network connection. Digitalization can also enable municipalities to respond to problematic realities which is the focus of one of the projects described in this entry.

¹⁴⁶ *Onlinezugangsgesetz* (OZG) enacted (jointly with other laws) on 14 August 2017 (BGBl. I S. 3122).

¹⁴⁷ Sec 1(1) OZG. The implementation of this obligation takes place in close cooperation between the federal and the *Länder* governments, as the law requires the creation of a joint online portal (*Portalverbund*) in Sec 1(2). The federal and the *Länder* governments established an organisation to oversee this cooperation, the federal IT-cooperation (FITKO), for further information see 'Das Onlinezugangsgesetz (OZG)' (*FITKO*) <<https://www.fitko.de/Start#StartFIM>> accessed 25 June 2020. A detailed overview on the cooperative projects is given here: 'Digitalisierungsprogramme' (*Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community*) <<https://www.onlinezugangsgesetz.de/Webs/OZG/DE/umsetzung/digitalisierungsprogramme/digitalisierungsprogramme-node.html>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁴⁸ *Gesetz über die elektronische Verwaltung in Bayern* [Law on the Electronic Administration in Bavaria] (*Bayerisches E-Government-Gesetz – BayEGovG*), enacted 22 December 2015. Most other states as well as the federal legislature have enacted similar laws, see, for a list of the state laws from mid-2019, 'Sachstand – E-Government in Deutschland Aktueller Stand auf Bundes- und Landesebene' (File no WD 3 - 3000 - 134/19, Research Services of the German Bundestag 2019) 9f (hereinafter: WD Report) <<https://www.bundestag.de/resource/blob/655082/32a17c3834d5c5c5d6f5a7232f0491c0/WD-3-134-19-pdf-data.pdf>>.

¹⁴⁹ It obliges LGs to offer citizens a way to communicate with them electronically (Art 3), but only encourages the actual provision of electronic/online services (Art 4).

Description of the Practice

Digitalization of course presupposes the existence of (broadband) infrastructure. While this aspect is described in the first entry to report section 2 on local responsibilities, this entry will focus on the implementation of digital tools/technology in the municipal sector and how this is an example for intergovernmental cooperation. The intergovernmental cooperation in the field of digitalization of municipal services follows a common approach regarding the division of competences, with the *Land* government providing financial and technical support while the LGs are tasked with the implementation itself.

The Bavarian Government is implementing several means to incentivize LGs to engage in digitalization. One project is a website named 'BayernPortal' that provides information to citizens and also LGs on (digital) governmental services.¹⁵⁰ Furthermore, the state set up a system enabling each Bavarian citizen to create its own account to access governmental services online, the so-called 'BayernID'. This system is supposed to be taken up by all LGs that implement digital provision of services.¹⁵¹ Another aspect is the inter-governmental financing of digitalization. Here, two state-administered funding programs are worth mentioning.

The first one is named Digital Town Hall (*Digitales Rathaus*) and is focused on subsidizing the digital transformation of LGs' administration. It grants funding (from *Länder* level) to specific LGs upon application in accordance with a Bavarian funding directive enacted in 2019.¹⁵² The directive pursues a holistic approach, as only concepts containing more than 20 online services in total are eligible for financing.¹⁵³ This shows that the directive wants an overarching digitalization instead of only special sectors of governmental services. However, the directive only applies to totally new online services and explicitly excludes the modernization/updating of preexisting services.¹⁵⁴ This is meant to increase the number of digital services offered by municipalities and to implement the requirements of the federal law (OZG) mentioned above.¹⁵⁵ A broadening of existing services could however be eligible for funding.¹⁵⁶ While urban local governments (ULGs) are not in general excluded from financing under the initiative, financing has so far been granted mostly to rural local governments (RLGs) (from North Bavaria,

¹⁵⁰ Accessible via the website <<http://www.freistaat.bayern/>>, also available in English (accessed 25 June 2020).

¹⁵¹ See, e.g., Sec 4(1)(1) of the funding directive for the project Digital town hall (see *infra* for further detail) that makes funding conditional upon the compatibility of digital projects with the BayernID-system.

¹⁵² *Richtlinie zur Förderung der Bereitstellung von Online-Diensten im kommunalen Bereich* [Regulation on the Promotion of the Provision of Online-Services in the Municipal Field] (*Förderrichtlinie digitales Rathaus – FöRdR*), BayMbl. 2019 no 290, 7 August 2019.

¹⁵³ Sec 4(1)(4).

¹⁵⁴ Secs 2; 4(1)(4); 4(2).

¹⁵⁵ Sec 1.

¹⁵⁶ Sec 4(1)(4).

as the funding allocation for South Bavarian LGs has not yet been announced).¹⁵⁷ This might be explained by the fact that most ULGs already have digital systems in place, which makes them ineligible for funding.

The second project is called Digital Village Bavaria (*Digitales Dorf Bayern*)¹⁵⁸ and picks specific pilot projects in RLGs that are meant to deal with upcoming challenges by employing the benefits of digitalization. In a first step, several regions (comprising several municipal LGs¹⁵⁹) were selected in a state-wide competition, the selection being based on concepts that were submitted by regions. The regional LGs were asked to identify challenges they are facing due to demographic change (e.g. public transport services becoming unprofitable, lack of qualified workforce, discontinuation of healthcare services, etc.¹⁶⁰) and to come up with digital concepts that are meant to help them tackle these challenges. Currently, there are five so-called pilot regions working in the project framework, each of them lying in a peripheral area of Bavaria.¹⁶¹ These regions receive (mostly financial) support in the development and implementation of their concept. Furthermore, each region will be marketed as an innovative region by the project and on its website.¹⁶²

Assessment of the Practice

While the Bavarian initiatives and accompanying statements by politicians and LGs show that the *Länder* government is focused on achieving e-government, there are some points that warrant attention. Most of the current programs focus mainly on RLGs. While ULGs might have more budgetary leeway to fund digitalization efforts by themselves, this could also be an indicator for a lagging implementation in RLGs (in comparison with ULGs). Especially the Digital Town Hall program is tailored towards these issues, as it only covers first-time digitalization. In this regard, the efforts seem to be driven mainly by the requirements of the federal legislation described above. Another factor for primarily funding RLGs is the need to tackle demographic changes, as a well-implemented digitalization could make rural areas more attractive for

¹⁵⁷ See for a list of the beneficiaries: 'Füracker und Gerlach: E-Government im Kommunalbereich ausbauen' (*Digitales Rathaus Bayern*) <<https://www.digitales-rathaus.bayern/aktuelles/news/artikel9.html>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁵⁸ See <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern>>. A similar project called digital villages (*Digitale Dörfer*) was set up in Rhineland Palatine and now caters to RLGs all over Germany. For further information and a list of the participating LGs see <<https://www.digitale-doefer.de/>> both accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁵⁹ The smallest region selected is made up of two municipalities, the biggest of 16.

¹⁶⁰ For a list of identified challenges, see 'Herausforderungen' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/dd-herausforderungen/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁶¹ See for a list of regions and the respective projects pursued: 'Übersicht der Pilotregionen' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/die-modelldoerfer/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁶² The benefits enjoyed by the pilot regions are listed here: 'Leistungsumfang' (*Digitales Dorf. Bayern Digital.*) <<https://digitales-dorf.bayern/index.php/dd-herausforderungen/leistungsumfang/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

companies and/or younger inhabitants.¹⁶³ This is explicitly addressed within the Digital Village project.

One could argue that these considerations exclude ‘experienced’ ULGs that would be able to test innovative projects more efficiently. While this does indeed not seem to be the main priority of the existing funding programs examined in this entry, it also becomes clear that the different circumstances in ULGs and RLGs render a ‘one fits all’-approach not feasible. To the contrary, funding programs that are able to take into account the individual circumstances will produce more fitting results. Changing circumstances in different regions as well as the rapid technological development in the field of digitalization also show that a continuous evaluation and adaption of existing programs is necessary.

Looking at the programs from the perspective of inter-governmental cooperation, the biggest disadvantage lies in the lack of a deeper cooperation between the different layers of government. Instead of setting up one or several centralized project(s) to engage in the (technical) development itself, it seems that the government (through centralized projects) merely funds initiatives on the LG level. While this enables the LGs to actually tailor the specific projects to their needs, it might lead to plenty of parallel research and development on similar projects. A centralized agency¹⁶⁴ that engages in development itself or provides general tools/services for LGs could be more efficient and should be broadened in scope beyond the ‘framework software’ described above. The lack of central development is also one of the aspects criticized by governmental authorities when surveyed on the implementation of e-government.¹⁶⁵ At the same time, it should not be overlooked that the Bavarian digital villages project is supposed to develop and test programs that could be feasible for other LGs too, using the pilot regions as a kind of testing labs.¹⁶⁶ Additionally, the federal and the *Länder* governments created the federal information management system (FIM)¹⁶⁷ to establish a platform where developed digital solutions can be made accessible to other governments/agencies.

¹⁶³ This idea is also ushered by the following report on a digital village in Rhineland-Palatine: ‘Leben auf dem Land. Ein Dorf wird digital’ (*Die Bundesregierung*, 9 August 2019) <<https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/themen/digitalisierung/digitales-dorf-1604066>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁶⁴ Such as the Government Technology Agency in Singapore, for further information see <<https://www.tech.gov.sg/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁶⁵ WD Report 14.97% of the agencies obliged to implement e-government services stated they are facing challenges in their implementation. Besides the lack of centrally developed IT solutions, the other substantial difficulties in the implementation referred to by governmental agencies/bodies are: lack of funding; data protection rules; lack of acceptance by users and lack of relevant competences within the agencies.

¹⁶⁶ A similar project (*Smarte Landregionen*) focusing on rural regions is also pursued by the federal government. The application phase for regions began in December 2019. For further information see ‘Smarte Landregionen’ (*BMEL.de*) https://www.bmel.de/DE/Laendliche-Raeume/Digitales/SmarteLandregionen/_texte/MuD_Smarte_LandRegionen.html accessed 25 June 2020.

¹⁶⁷ Further explanation on this process is provided on <<https://fimpportal.de/>> accessed 25 June 2020.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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